

Imaging Protocol Addendum:

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We imaged each honey bee specimen using a Macropod Pro 3D imaging system (Macroscopic Solutions, LLC, East Hartford, CT, USA) equipped with a Canon EOS 6D Mark II camera and a Canon RF 65–100 mm Macro USM lens mounted on a motorized rotational stage. To illuminate the specimens, we positioned two external flashes on either side of the imaging stage. Light was diffused using two custom 3D-printed diffusers: one dome-shaped diffuser placed over the specimen and a flat circular diffuser attached directly to the camera lens. A black felt background was used to minimize shadows and create high contrast between the specimen and the background.

Specimens were mounted on insect pins and secured to a wax base on the rotating stage. Each bee was manually tilted approximately 15° so both dorsal and ventral surfaces were visible within a single rotation. Specimens were left in their natural condition; wings, legs, and other appendages were not repositioned to avoid causing damage. Specimens were briefly checked for dust and alignment before imaging, and adjustments were made to ensure the body remained fully within the frame throughout the 360° rotation.

All photographs were taken using manual settings, with a fixed aperture of f/8 and a custom Kelvin white balance between 4000K to 6000K, applied consistently across specimens. Flash settings, ISO and shutter speed were adjusted as needed for image quality. The camera was set to manual focus throughout the imaging procedure. For each specimen, we performed a 370° rotation on the y-axis to ensure full coverage of all surfaces. The Stackshot system was programmed to capture 140 rotational steps during this rotation, automatically calculating equal angular increments.

At each rotation angle, the Stackshot macrorail executed an automated focus-stacking sequence along the x-axis. The operator set the beginning and end focus points by manually focusing just behind and just in front of the specimen, respectively. A consistent step distance of 0.952 mm was used for all specimens, and the Stackshot system calculated the number of images captured in each stack automatically based on this distance. All source images were captured as JPEGs and stored on an external hard drive. Image sets for each specimen were then divided into individual folders—approximately 141 folders, one for each rotational position—using FolderAxe software. Each image set was then stacked into one single image, resulting in 141 stacked TIFF images per specimen.

Focus stacking was performed in Zerene Stacker using the Align + PMax method, with no additional parameter adjustments and no manual retouching. The stacked TIFF files generated by Zerene Stacker were then batch-processed in Adobe Photoshop. Processing consisted of a standardized action that first applied a curves adjustment layer to standardize and deepen the black background, followed by a Smart Sharpen filter with a threshold of 3. These steps were applied both to specimen images and to control

images, including the scale bar, color block, and background reference. Final images were exported as high-quality JPEGs (quality 12, 6240 × 4160 px, 72 dpi) without cropping or masking.

Quality control involved reviewing each specimen's stacked images for clarity, completeness of rotation, and consistent lighting. Specimens were reimaged if the rotation or stacking sequence was interrupted or if image quality was compromised, provided the specimen remained intact and available. The post-processed JPEG image sets were then transferred to collaborators responsible for the 3D modeling workflow.

Section Format:

Imaging System and Lighting Setup

Specimens were imaged using a Macropod Pro 3D imaging system (Macroscopic Solutions, LLC, East Hartford, CT, USA) equipped with a Canon EOS 6D Mark II camera and a Canon RF 65–100 mm Macro USM lens. Illumination was provided by two external flashes positioned laterally on the imaging stage. Light was diffused using two custom 3D-printed diffusers: a dome-shaped diffuser placed over the specimen and a flat circular diffuser mounted on the camera lens. A black felt background was used to minimize shadows and enhance contrast.

Specimen Mounting and Positioning

Each honey bee specimen was mounted on an insect pin and attached to a wax base on the rotating stage. The specimen was manually tilted approximately 15° prior to imaging to allow simultaneous dorsal and ventral visualization during rotation. Appendages were left in their natural positions to avoid damaging specimens. Minor dust removal and centering adjustments were performed as needed.

Image Capture and Rotation Protocol

Images were taken using manual camera settings with a fixed aperture of f/8 and a constant Kelvin white balance between 4000K to 6000K. ISO and shutter speed were adjusted between specimens to optimize exposure. The camera remained in manual focus mode throughout. Each specimen was rotated through 370° on the y-axis, and the Stackshot system captured 140 rotational steps, automatically calculating the angular interval.

Focus Stacking Procedure

At each rotational position, a focus stack was captured along the x-axis using the Stackshot macrorail. The operator manually set the starting focus (just behind the specimen) and ending focus (just in front). A constant step size of 0.952 mm was applied for all stacks, and the Stackshot system automatically determined the total number of images per stack. All images were captured as JPEGs and organized into 141 folders using FolderAxe software, with folder names corresponding to specimen catalog numbers.

Each image set was then stacked into one single image, resulting in 141 stacked TIFF images per specimen.

Image Stacking and Post-Processing

Focus stacks were processed in Zerene Stacker (Zerene Systems LLC) using the Align + PMax method with default parameters and without retouching. Output TIFF files were batch-processed in Adobe Photoshop using a standardized action consisting of (1) a curves adjustment to standardize black backgrounds and (2) application of Smart Sharpen (threshold = 3). Stacked images and control images (scale bar, color block, background) were processed using the same batch settings. Final images were exported as JPEGs (quality 12, 6240 × 4160 px, 72 dpi) with no cropping or masking.

Quality Control and Data Output

Specimens with damaged structures, incomplete rotations, or inconsistent lighting were flagged for reimaging if available. Final processed JPEG image suites were provided to collaborators for 3D model construction and morphometric analysis. All modeling steps were performed by entomology collaborators and are not included in this imaging protocol.